

The privilege to select: a metabolic role for the tumor suppressor PML

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Altered metabolism is one of the hallmarks of cancer. One example is the well-known Warburg effect in which tumors generate lactate from glucose at ten-fold higher rates than normal tissues even under non-hypoxic (normoxic) conditions[1]. The underlying mechanism and the consequences of such a change during cancer development are not completely understood and remain active research topics. Mutations or aberrant expression of oncogenes and tumor suppressors are the prevailing driving force of cancer development. These abnormalities also define paradigms of cancer metabolism. Cheng and colleagues now report that a well-known tumor suppressor, promyelocytic leukemia protein (PML), is a critical regulator of fatty acid oxidation and carbohydrate metabolism in mice[2].

Under normal physiological conditions, PML is ubiquitously expressed in almost every tissue. PML is an essential component of a specialized nuclear sub-domain named PML nuclear bodies (NBs). These are proteinaceous depots where PML is transiently or constitutively associated with a variety of interacting partners including transcription factors and enzymes involved in diverse cellular processes[3]. Thus, the PML NBs serve as a nuclear reservoir that may sequester proteins to limit their accessibility or to change their activity. As such, PML is believed to participate in a variety of fundamental cellular processes[4]. Environmental cues such as nutrients, cytokines and growth factors either promote or disrupt these interactions, resulting in changes in the size and number of the PML NBs[4]. Consequently, loss of PML leads to dysregulated signaling and pathological conditions.

The current study characterized the metabolic consequences of PML knockout in mice. One of the striking findings in this study was the identification of PML as a gatekeeper for the metabolic machinery that chooses energy sources, such as fat or carbohydrate. From an evolutionary point of view, metabolic flexibility and adaptability are keys for mouse survival. For example, when fed a carbohydrate and fat balanced normal chow diet during the daily feeding-fasting cycle; wild type (WT) mice oscillate their metabolic fuels between carbohydrates following feeding and fat during fasting. On the other hand, during prolonged feeding of a fat-enriched diet, such as Western style diet,

fat becomes favored fuel over carbohydrate at all times. These fuel choices are considered beneficial for the animals' own survival in response to changing environmental challenges (Diets). Interestingly, PML knock-out (KO) mice seem to lose this flexibility and adaptability. When fed a normal chow diet, the KO mice showed a marked preference for fat utilization over carbohydrate utilization. Notably, the carbohydrate metabolizing capacity of the KO mice seems to be lower than the WT mice as evidenced by the KO mice showing acute hyperglycemia and insulin tolerance. This observation echoes the Randle cycle proposed by Philip Randle and colleagues[5] that fatty acid metabolism and glucose metabolism are reciprocally co-regulated and dysregulation of one process has an impact on the other.

Metabolic flexibility and adaptability are inherently associated with genomic information. The authors propose that disruption of PML re-patterns the transcriptional activities of panels of metabolic genes in key metabolic tissues, such as liver and muscle, which in turn defines the fat-burning preference observed in the KO mice. Therefore, the PML KO mice display a rigid metabolic paradigm that lacks adaptability to different diets. This inspired the authors to challenge the mice with a diet containing a high fat content (Western style diet). Given that PML KO mice favor fat utilization, it was expected that PML KO mice would be better suited to a Western style diet than their WT counterparts. Indeed, the KO mice were healthier and leaner than the WT mice following feeding on the Western style diet.

Collectively, these novel findings suggest that PML is a critical metabolic regulator that determines the choice of fuel. As PML protein abundance is low in most cancer tissues, this study further adds insight into cancer metabolism by dissecting the role of PML in fatty acid oxidation and carbohydrate metabolism.

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